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Fast binaural processing but sluggish masker representation reconfiguration

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ABSTRACT:

Perceptual organization of complex acoustic scenes requires fast binaural processing for accurate localization or lateralization based on short single-source-dominated glimpses. This sensitivity also manifests in the ability to detect rapid oscillating interaural time and phase differences as well as interaural correlation. However, binaural processing has also been termed “sluggish” based on experiments that require binaural detection in a masker with an additional binaural cue change in temporal proximity. The present study shows that the temporal integration windows obtained from data on binaural sluggishness cannot account for the detection of rapid binaural oscillations. A model with fast IPD encoding but a slower process of updating the internal representation of the masker IPD statistics accounted for both experiments of the “fast” and the “sluggish” categories. © 2023 Author(s). All article content, except where otherwise noted, is licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY) license (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>). <https://doi.org/10.1121/10.0021072>

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I. INTRODUCTION

The extraordinary precision of encoding interaural phase difference (IPD) allows for binaural unmasking and low-frequency sound localization. Psychophysical characterization of binaural unmasking and sound localization, however, led to different interpretations concerning the processing speed of the binaural system. On the one hand, subjects are able to lateralize and detect a change in ITD as brief as 3–6 ms (Reed *et al.*, 2016). Also, detection thresholds of broadband binaural beat or “Phase warp” stimuli (Siveke *et al.*, 2008) or of oscillating interaural correlation [“Oscor” stimulus (Gatehouse and Akeroyd, 2006; Grantham, 1982; Grantham and Wightman, 1979; Siveke *et al.*, 2008)] embedded in uncorrelated noise have been measured up to beat or oscillation frequencies of 1024 and 128 Hz, respectively (Siveke *et al.*, 2008). All of these are indicators of very fast binaural processing. Modeling suggested that the temporal resolution is primarily limited only by the bandwidth of the auditory filters (Dietz *et al.*, 2008), i.e., their ring time. On the other hand, many tone-in-noise detection experiments have led to the interpretation of a “sluggish” binaural system. For example, Kollmeier and Gilkey (1990) found elevated detection thresholds for an antiphasic tone (S_π) in temporal proximity of an inversion of the masker’s IPD. When the masker changed from antiphasic N_π , which gives no binaural benefit, to N0, thresholds drop only gradually as the target tone burst is moved away

from the transition moment. For a full binaural unmasking over 100 ms separation is required, much more than in monaural forward masking experiments. The data were well fitted by a double-sided exponential integration window with equivalent rectangular durations (ERD) in the range $33.2 \leq \text{ERD} \leq 83.2$ ms. When replacing the IPD inversion by a diotic 15 dB masker attenuation, integration times of only $11.9 \leq \text{ERD} \leq 26.0$ ms were fitted. Binaural sluggishness was also supported by Grantham and Wightman (1979). They used the above-mentioned oscillating interaural correlation “Oscor” noise as a masker and presented a short interaurally out of phase (S_π) tone pip coinciding with a moment where the instantaneous masker correlation is either 1 or -1 , i.e., where the masker briefly resembled N0 or N_π , respectively. The binaural masking level difference (BMLD) disappeared already at a modulation frequency of 4 Hz. Grantham and Wightman (1979) explained the effect by assuming different monaural and binaural temporal analysis windows with binaural integration times of $44 \leq \text{ERD} \leq 140$ ms. However, averaging interaural cues over such a long time window is likely to conflict with the “fast” studies mentioned above. To our knowledge there is no model that can account for both classes of experimental data without significantly changing the integration time constant.

We hypothesize interaural differences to be encoded with a high temporal resolution primarily limited by peripheral filter ring times. Furthermore, we follow the hypothesis of Yost (1985), who suggested that binaural unmasking relies on an estimate of the masker parameters. We hypothesize that if a task requires re-estimation of masker parameters, this higher-stage operation is the cause of the sluggish behavior. The two possible cases can be exemplified with the Oscor stimulus: As the oscillation frequency increases,

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the changes in perceived masker width move closer in time to the target tone, interfering with detection by reducing the contrast in perceived width between target and masker. This means the widening cue induced by the antiphase target tone is disrupted by the widening and narrowing induced by the correlation oscillations of the masker. The instantaneous correlation of the masker at the moment the target is added cannot be exploited by human listeners (Grantham and Wightman, 1979). In contrast, if the task is to detect the presence of the oscillating correlation in a static masker, the estimation process is not needed. In this case, the auditory system can exploit the few millisecond short moments of high correlation (Siveke *et al.*, 2008). The rapid sensory encoding of IPD allows these rapid modulations to be perceived as a fluttering or intra-head rotation pattern (Witton *et al.*, 2000), which is the primary cue for such a task.

In this work we first show that the temporal integration windows obtained from data on binaural detection close in time to a masker IPD change (sluggish category) cannot account for the detection of rapid correlation oscillations. We then suggest a model with fast IPD encoding but a slow reformation of the internal representation of the masker. To simulate reduced sensitivity in temporal proximity to masker IPD changes, the model compares the stimulus internal representation to a template. As this template, a low-pass filtered internal representation of the masker is used. The low pass resembles the sluggish reorganization of the internal masker representation. Without changes to the model or its temporal parameters, it can account for both, data that requires fast and data that previously required sluggish binaural processing.

II. SIMULATIONS

A. Temporal integration does not account for oscillating correlation detection

We exemplarily tested whether the integration windows derived from studies that fall into the sluggish category can still be compatible with detection of rapid oscillations of interaural correlation (Siveke *et al.*, 2008). The integrations times fitted by Kollmeier and Gilkey (1990) ($33.2 \leq \text{ERD} \leq 83.2$ ms) are similar to Holube *et al.* (1998) in their comparable step condition ($40 \leq \text{ERD} \leq 69$ ms). Replacing the masker correlation step with a cosine correlation oscillation, as in the cosine condition of Holube *et al.* (1998) and the similar experiment of Grantham and Wightman (1979), resulted in longer windows of $91 \leq \text{ERD} \leq 122$ ms and $44 \leq \text{ERD} \leq 140$ ms, respectively.

The peak-to-peak interaural correlation of an unmasked, gammatone-filtered Oscor stimulus can be reduced by temporal integration at the output of the binaural interaction. We compared the peak-to-peak correlation after temporal integration to the just-noticeable difference (JND) from zero correlation which is 0.3 (Boehnke *et al.*, 2002). We used an oscillation frequency of 64 Hz being the highest of the modulation frequencies measured by Siveke *et al.* (2008) that can be preserved by a gammatone filter centered at 500 Hz. If the

peak-to-peak modulation of interaural correlation of the filtered Oscor stimulus exceeds the JND of 0.3, we expect that the corresponding time constant allows for the detection of oscillating correlation as reported by Siveke *et al.* (2008).

Figure 1(A) shows the interaural correlation resulting from gammatone-filtering and temporal integration using a double-sided exponential integration window with ERDs in the range reported in the literature. While the correlation modulation in the stimulus oscillates between -1.0 and $+1.0$, it is already reduced to the range $[-0.5 \ 0.5]$ by gammatone filtering. Figure 1(B) shows that any applied temporal integration with $\text{ERD} > 10$ ms reduced the peak-to-peak correlation below the estimated JND (dotted line). Integration windows of, e.g., $\text{ERD} = 30$ ms (i.e., $\tau = 15$ ms for a double-sided exponential window) are already below the lower boundary of all models that fall into the sluggish category but at the same time they are far too large to preserve any perceivable correlation from the Oscor. For comparison: The double-sided exponential window used in the comprehensive and widely used model of Breebaart *et al.* (2001) had an ERD of 60 ms. Thus, we conclude that detection of rapid correlation modulation cannot be explained by the integration time constants that have been widely attributed to binaural detection and we cannot find any “compromise integration window” satisfying both categories.

FIG. 1. (Color online) (A) Oscor stimulus where the interaural correlation is modulated with 64 Hz after gammatone filtering and temporal integration using a double-sided exponential window with different ERDs. (B) Resulting peak-to-peak correlation for the Oscor stimulus as shown in (A). The dashed lines at ± 0.15 in (A) and $+0.3$ in (B) denote the assumed JND to detect the modulation.

B. A model for both fast and sluggish processing

Having observed that temporal integration of interaural correlation alone cannot explain results on detecting rapid modulations and at the same time sluggishness, we developed a model with the goal to account for the aforementioned categories at the same time. It was designed to reproduce listeners' behavior expected from the stimulus as processed according to our hypothesis: Interaural differences are available for detection with the temporal resolution only limited by basilar-membrane processing, at least at frequencies below about 1000 Hz. Binaural sluggishness accordingly appears if a change in masker IPD statistics, entailing reformation of its internal representation, interferes with target-in-masker detection. In this model, the internal representation includes the instantaneous interaural correlation, coherence, and phase.

1. Peripheral processing

The left and right input signals were processed with a fourth-order gammatone filter. This represents basilar-membrane bandpass filtering. The filterbank implementation by Hohmann (2002) was used. The tone-in-noise experiments that we exemplarily chose for the present single-channel simulations (Buss and Hall, 2011; Grantham and Wightman, 1979; Kollmeier and Gilkey, 1990) determined the used filter center frequency to be 500 Hz. The filter bandwidth (ERB = 79 Hz) or its corresponding ring time (ERD = 6.3 ms) limits the speed with which interaural cues can change, also the experiments by Siveke *et al.* (2008) are simulated only at 500 Hz, to keep a fair comparison that is not influenced by employing higher frequency channels and thus filters with a shorter ring time.

2. Binaural processing

The instantaneous complex correlation coefficient $\gamma(t)$ serves as the internal representation. It was derived from the analytical (i.e., complex-valued) left and right signals $l(t)$ and $r(t)$ provided by the gammatone filter

$$\gamma(t) = \left\langle \frac{l^*(t)r(t)}{\sqrt{|l(t)|^2|r(t)|^2}} \right\rangle, \quad (1)$$

where an asterisk denotes the complex conjugate and $\langle \bullet \rangle$ the average over an ensemble of stimulus tokens.¹ $\gamma(t)$ was used because it conveniently combines information about the instantaneous interaural correlation $\rho(t) = \Re\{\gamma(t)\}$, instantaneous coherence $|\gamma(t)|$ and instantaneous IPD $\arg\{\gamma(t)\}$ (Encke and Dietz, 2022). The resulting binaural display represents the information available to the detector.

The hypothesis of a gradual reformation of the masker internal representation resulted from the observation that binaural detection is impaired in the presence of an interaurally modulated masker but not for detection of a modulated target. We modeled the gradual reformation of the internal representation of the masker by employing a parallel path in

which $\gamma(t)$ of a masker-alone version of the stimulus involved low-pass filtering. A double-sided exponential window with a time constant of $\tau = 30$ ms for each lobe was used. The ERD was thus $2\tau = 2 \times 30$ ms = 60 ms, oriented on the window fits by Kollmeier and Gilkey (1990) and on the ERD = 60 ms used in the model of Breebaart *et al.* (2001),

$$\gamma_{M,lp}(t) = \left\langle \text{lp} \left(\frac{l^*(t)r(t)}{\sqrt{|l(t)|^2|r(t)|^2}} \right) \right\rangle. \quad (2)$$

Subsequent to the reformation-mimicking low-pass filtering, the average over an ensemble of 200 stimulus tokens was used in Eqs. (1) and (2). This describes the expected behavior of a group of listeners after many repetitions of the experiment. As the results of Kollmeier and Gilkey (1990) reveal comparable binaural forward and backward masking effects, a zero-phase forward-reverse filter was used. The internal representation of the masker $\gamma_{M,lp}(t)$ is then contrasted with the internal representation of the complete stimulus $\gamma(t)$, i.e., masker plus target without low-pass filtering. The real parts of $\gamma(t)$ and $\gamma_{M,lp}(t)$, i.e., interaural correlation, are plotted in Fig. 2. For stimuli with changing masker correlation, such as Kollmeier and Gilkey (1990), the difference between template and target is therefore reduced in temporal proximity to the masker correlation change,

FIG. 2. (Color online) Real part [i.e., interaural correlation $\rho(t)$] of the stimulus internal representation $\gamma(t)$ and of the masker internal representation $\gamma_{M,lp}(t)$, as used in the present model. Arrows symbolize the maximum possible binaural cue. (A) Stimulus as used in Kollmeier and Gilkey (1990) with 80 ms delay time between the masker changing from N_π to N_0 and the S_π target; SNR = -16 dB. (B) Oscor stimulus as used in Siveke *et al.* (2008). Oscillation frequency 64 Hz, SNR = 4 dB.

reducing the detection cue. An oscillating correlation or Phasewarp (Siveke *et al.*, 2008), however, is preserved as the required temporal precision is still available to the detector from the unfiltered target $\gamma(t)$. The low-pass filtering prior to the ensemble averaging in the internal representation of the masker represents the hypothesis that a comparatively slow adaptation to a change in the $\gamma(t)$ statistics of the masker impairs detection. This means, the binaural feature allows both detection of an oscillating pattern and detection of a change in perceived width with the same backend.

As in Encke and Dietz (2022) and Eurich *et al.* (2022), the unity-limited interaural representations $\gamma(t)$ and $\gamma_{M,lp}(t)$ are Fisher z (i.e., inverse hyperbolic tangent) transformed for the purpose of variance normalization (Just and Bamler, 1994; McNemar, 1969), as often applied in psychophysics [e.g., Bernstein and Trahiotis (2017) and Lüddemann *et al.* (2007)]. $\gamma(t)$ and $\gamma_{M,lp}(t)$ are multiplied by a model parameter $\hat{\rho} < 1$ (Encke and Dietz, 2022; Eurich *et al.*, 2022) to avoid an infinite sensitivity to deviations from a coherence of unity. This is equivalent to adding uncorrelated noise to the two input signals. The inner representation of the binaural pathway is thus

$$\zeta(t) = z[\hat{\rho}\gamma(t)], \tag{3}$$

$$\zeta_{M,lp}(t) = z[\hat{\rho}\gamma_{M,lp}(t)], \tag{4}$$

where $z[\cdot]$ is the Fisher z -transform applied to the modulus of $\gamma(t)$ while leaving the argument unchanged.

The model extracts the instantaneous absolute difference between the internal representations of the stimulus and that of the masker,

$$b(t) = |\zeta(t) - \zeta_{M,lp}(t)|. \tag{5}$$

As the model was required to detect ongoing temporal patterns, a sequence of independent observations was extracted, based on the multiple-looks principle (Viemeister and Wakefield, 1989). These observations are combined in an optimal manner,

$$b_{opt} = \sqrt{\sum_t b(t)^2}. \tag{6}$$

The model parameter σ_{bin} represents the standard deviation of an internal noise with a Gaussian distribution of amplitudes. It adjusts the sensitivity of the binaural path in order to model the sensitivity index d'_{bin} of discriminating between the noise alone (N) interval and the signal plus noise (S + N) interval,

$$d'_{bin} = \frac{b_{opt,S+N} - b_{opt,N}}{\sigma_{bin}}. \tag{7}$$

The optimal combination in a multiple-looks manner [Eq. (6)] enables the model to inherently code higher sensitivity for longer detection cues.

3. Monaural processing

In order to simulate experiments that compare binaural and monaural processing speed, we also designed a simple monaural path. It is sensitive to changes in stimulus instantaneous envelope power $P(t)$. The envelope is the modulus of the complex-valued filter output. For the stimuli employed in this study, it is sufficient to evaluate only one side. Similar to the binaural path, the temporal resolution of $P(t)$ is only limited by the ring time of the gammatone filter (ERD = 6.3 ms). The model considers the difference in ensemble-average envelope power between the signal-plus-noise and noise-alone intervals,

$$\Delta P(t) = \langle P_{N+S}(t) \rangle - \langle P_N(t) \rangle. \tag{8}$$

As in the binaural pathway, the instantaneous power differences $\Delta P(t)$ are treated as independent observations and thus combined in an optimal manner,

$$\Delta P_{opt} = \sqrt{\sum_t \left[\frac{\Delta P(t)}{\langle P_N(t) \rangle} \right]^2}. \tag{9}$$

The processing accuracy is limited by a level-dependent internal noise with a Gaussian distribution of amplitudes and a standard deviation of σ_{mon} (Eurich *et al.*, 2022),

$$d'_{mon} = \frac{\Delta P_{opt}}{\sigma_{mon}}. \tag{10}$$

C. Quantitative predictions of detection thresholds

We used the described model as shown in Fig. 3 to estimate detection thresholds across different experiments. The sensitivity indices d' of monaural and binaural path are therefore combined to the overall sensitivity index, assuming independent information channels (Green and Swets, 1966),

$$d'_{bin+mon} = \sqrt{d_{bin}^2 + d_{mon}^2}. \tag{11}$$

The d' that corresponds to the experiment-specific detection thresholds was obtained via table-lookup [numerical evaluation in Hacker and Ratcliff (1979)]. This depends on the number of intervals as well as the specific staircase procedure used in the simulated experiments. As in Eurich *et al.* (2022), for each condition the model was evaluated for a range of target levels. This provided the psychometric function. The predicted detection threshold was obtained from a linear fit to the logarithmic d' . The model parameters σ_{bin} and σ_{mon} were manually adjusted to optimize the prediction accuracy. The resulting parameter values are given in Table I. The aim was to see whether a single detector with a single time constant can at the same time account for different paradigms supporting fast and sluggish processing, rather than to maximize precision concerning a certain paradigm. The following experiments were chosen as a

FIG. 3. Flowchart of the model as used to quantitatively predict binaural detection thresholds. Dashed arrows symbolize that the sensitivity indices d' are obtained by comparing signal-plus-noise with noise-alone.

representative selection concerning evidence for fast and sluggish binaural processing. All experiments can be simulated based on the output of a single bandpass filter centered at 500 Hz. This ensures that IPDs in the temporal fine structure are the dominant cue for detection and allows for a good comparison. Figure 4 shows experimental thresholds and predictions with continuous lines denoting predictions for conditions with partly different IPDs of masker and target tone, dotted lines conditions where masker and tone always have the same IPD.

Due to the good agreement between simulations and the critical trends in the data, the experiments are described together with the predictions.

1. Kollmeier and Gilkey (1990)

A 20-ms 500 Hz S_π tone is to be detected in a 750-ms noise masker whose interaural correlation changes from 1 to

-1, or vice versa, after 375 ms. This means the tone interaural correlation (-1) differs from the masker interaural correlation only when appearing in either the first or the second half of the masker. Tone detection thresholds were reported as a function of the delay time of the tone relative to the moment of masker correlation change. The 0 dB point corresponds to each subject's and the model's detection thresholds for a reference $N_\pi S_\pi$ condition with a static masker, respectively. Experimental thresholds and simulations are shown in Fig. 4(A). Thresholds are highest when the S_π tone is presented during the N_π segment and are gradually getting lower as the tone is moved to the N0 part of the masker. Quantitatively, however, considerable differences are apparent across subjects. The predictions are generally within the range of the data. In another condition, instead of providing an interaural cue, one half of the masker was attenuated by 15 dB. The fact that thresholds were elevated up to about 120 ms into the N0 part but now only about 20 ms into the attenuated part has in the past been interpreted as a longer binaural than monaural temporal analysis window or sluggish binaural processing. This considerably steeper threshold decrease is clearly reproduced by the model. Subjects sometimes performed worse in the conditions with the IPD or SNR transitions in the masker, albeit up to 200 ms apart, than in the $N_\pi S_\pi$ reference condition with a static masker, as indicated by thresholds above 0 dB. The model, however, predicts the same thresholds in both cases, as expected. The fact that thresholds rise shortly before the masker level transition in Fig. 4(A), lower left panel, is so-called backward masking. Because the present model does not include the cortical effects associated with backward masking (Zwicker and Fastl, 1999), thresholds do not increase for tones appearing before the masker level increase. This leads to a slight offset between the data and the predictions, while the slope is reproduced, being much steeper than in the conditions with a masker IPD switch.

2. Grantham and Wightman (1979)

Figure 4(B) shows data and simulations for a second example on binaural sluggishness. As pointed out in the Introduction, the interaural correlation of the masker oscillates between -1 and +1 (Oscor). The target tone—a gated 17-ms 500-Hz S_π tone pip—was presented either at moments when the interaural correlation was 1 or -1. If the

TABLE I. Summary of the simulated experiments and predictions. Columns 1–3: Simulated experiment, rough category of binaural processing speed concluded by the authors, target signal. Columns 4–7: Used model parameters. $\hat{\rho} < 1$: Maximum coherence (internal noise); σ_{bin} : Standard deviation of the internal noise to determine the absolute performance of the binaural path; σ_{mon} : Standard deviation of the level-dependent internal noise to determine the acuity of the monaural pathway; equivalent rectangular duration of the temporal window used for the template.

Experiment	Category	Target	$\hat{\rho}$	σ_{bin}	σ_{mon}	ERD / ms
Kollmeier and Gilkey (1990)	sluggish	S_π	0.9	12	500	60
Grantham and Wightman (1979)	sluggish	S_π	0.9	20	350	60
Siveke et al. (2008)	fast	Oscor, Phasewarp	0.9	22	200	60
Dietz et al. (2008)	fast	Phasewarp	0.9	22	200	60
Buss and Hall (2011)	fast	S_0, S_π	0.9	20	200	60

FIG. 4. (Color online) Simulation results for four exemplary data sets on sluggish and fast binaural processing. Symbols denote the original experimental thresholds with filled symbols for the conditions on binaural detection and open symbols for those on monaural detection. Continuous lines denote model predictions for binaural, dotted lines for monaural detection conditions. See main text for experimental details.

S_π tone coincides with the correlated, i.e., momentarily NO-like masker, binaural unmasking is only evident at the very slowest oscillation frequencies of 0.5 or 1 Hz. At 4 Hz there is already virtually no binaural benefit anymore, which has been interpreted as evidence for binaural sluggishness. All features in the data are captured by the model. Predictions are within the range of between-subject deviations.

3. Siveke et al. (2008)

In this study, rapidly oscillating interaural cues serve as target, providing evidence for fast binaural processing, with experimental results and simulations plotted in Fig. 4(D). Wideband noise was generated that had fast changing interaural cues. Two types of interaural cue changes were employed: (1) Oscillating interaural correlation between -1 and $+1$ (Oscor); (2) a binaural beat, i.e., a linearly increasing and phase-wrapping IPD (Phasewarp). Both types of interaurally modulated noise could be detected in

interaurally uncorrelated noise up to modulation frequencies of 128 Hz and 1024 Hz in case of the Phasewarp. The oscillation—or beat-rate limit—is thus more than one order of magnitude higher than in the above-mentioned data by Grantham and Wightman (1979), where the Oscor is employed as a masker. Our model replicates at the same time sluggish behavior [Oscor as masker (Grantham and Wightman, 1979)] and non-sluggish behavior [Oscor/Phasewarp as target (Siveke et al., 2008)]. The sensitivity decline to detect very rapidly oscillating correlation or phase (64 Hz) is due to the auditory filter bandwidth. The interaurally correlated frequency components are separated by the modulation frequency. Thus, the corresponding left-right filter pairs see increasingly uncorrelated components. Increasing the center frequency of our analysis filter will allow detecting even higher Phasewarp frequencies, as reported by Siveke et al. (2008). However, the modulation frequencies encoded by the 500 Hz filter (i.e., up to 64 Hz) are sufficient in order to account for the category of fast binaural processing, as opposite to sluggish processing. The

fact that Dietz *et al.* (2008) obtained similar thresholds for a phase-warp band-limited to 0–550 Hz, we assume that for this type of sensitivity always arises from within-channel cues, rendering the simplistic single-channel model sufficient for this task and most comparable to the other tasks.

4. Buss and Hall (2011)

In contrast to Kollmeier and Gilkey (1990), the tone-in-noise detection data by Buss and Hall (2011) suggest comparably fast binaural and monaural processing [Fig. 4(C)]. The difference is that now the masker is attenuated for various durations but, in contrast to Kollmeier and Gilkey (1990) and Grantham and Wightman (1979), there is no change in the interaural configuration. N_0S_0 and N_0S_π thresholds are presented for a 20 ms long, ramped 500 Hz tone in wideband noise as a function of the duration of the 20 dB masker attenuation. The tone was either centered in or 20 ms shifted from the center of the attenuated part. The decreases in thresholds towards higher signal/masker intervals are considerably steeper than in the conditions in Kollmeier and Gilkey (1990) involving the masker-IPD transition. Furthermore, in contrast to Kollmeier and Gilkey (1990), thresholds decrease equally steep for both diotic and dichotic conditions. The model replicates these two core features of this experiment. However, predictions show a somewhat harder knee-point in thresholds than the data. This effect is associated with neural rate adaptation which was not employed in the present model in order to focus on the temporal processing hypothesis.

III. DISCUSSION

Binaural processing has been shown to be similarly fast as monaural processing in detection of interaural cue modulations (Dietz *et al.*, 2008; Siveke *et al.*, 2008), tone-in-noise detection (Bischof *et al.*, 2023; Buss and Hall, 2011), ITD and ILD detection (Akeroyd and Bernstein, 2001), and alternating-ITD lateralization (Reed *et al.*, 2016) tasks. On the other hand, it has been characterized “sluggish” in other detection (Culling and Summerfield, 1998; Grantham and Wightman, 1979; Holube *et al.*, 1998; Kolarik and Culling, 2009; Kollmeier and Gilkey, 1990), ITD discrimination (Kolarik and Culling, 2009), and speech intelligibility (Culling and Mansell, 2013; Hauth and Brand, 2018) tasks. We confirm previous statements that different tasks involve different aspects of binaural temporal processing (Akeroyd and Bernstein, 2001)—there is no compromise integration time accounting for both categories at the same time. With this result being very clear, such a compromise integration window is also not expected from other window shapes, such as a combination of a strongly weighted shorter and less weighted longer window as used by Bernstein *et al.* (2001). Instead, we accounted for a set of experiments from both categories with a model that compares an interval’s internal representation to a low-pass filtered internal representation of the masker. This is a simplistic implementation

of our hypothesis: Binaural sluggishness appears when detecting a static target in an interaurally modulated masker but not when detecting a modulated target in a static masker. This is a result of a slow reformation of the masker internal representation or, in other words, an adaptation of the interaural masker profile estimate (Yost, 1985).

Such reformation takes effect in experiments as performed by Kollmeier and Gilkey (1990). There, the masker IPD is inverted (correlation is changed from -1 to 1), causing a change in its perceived spatiality (i.e., width). This interferes with the target cue which is also a change in perceived spatiality, because the S_π target causes IPD fluctuations when added to a diotic masker. Similarly, when adding an S_π target at the positive peak of a masker correlation oscillation (Grantham and Wightman, 1979), the continuously changing perceived masker spatiality interferes with target-induced widening. Hauth and Brand (2018) measured speech reception thresholds for spoken sentences in the presence of a masking noise with modulated IPD. Binaural unmasking was found to decay for modulation frequencies up to 4 Hz, similar to the above-mentioned tone-in-noise experiment by Grantham and Wightman (1979). We hypothesize the same across-time interference of the masker spatiality to limit binaural unmasking of speech in the presence of an interaurally modulated masker.

In contrast, to detect the correlation modulation as a target in uncorrelated noise (Siveke *et al.*, 2008), the perceived fluttering is sufficient. Thus, fast modulations in correlation can be detected while the accompanying width changes of an additional tone cannot (Singh and Bharadwaj, 2021; Witton *et al.*, 2000). In Buss and Hall (2011) no sluggishness was observed although the dichotic condition requires interaural cue detection. Their masker, however, contained only an attenuation, no phase or correlation change and therefore no change in masker IPD statistics. The presented model preserves fast temporal fluctuations because temporal integration only affects the IPD template of the internal representation of the masker. Thus, the model accounts for all mentioned stimulus categories.

Temporal-analysis-window lengths fitted to experimental results indicating sluggishness [e.g., Grantham and Wightman (1979), Holube *et al.* (1998), and Kollmeier and Gilkey (1990)] extend over a wide range, both across studies but also across subjects within a study. This indicates that binaural sluggishness is not a fixed, inevitable phenomenon determined by the statistics of the interaural cues or by a hard-wired temporal integration but rather a consequence of an individual’s decoding or interpretation of the encoded cues. According to Yasin and Henning (2012) such is consistent with McFadden (1966), Robinson and Trahiotis (1972), and Yost (1985), reasoning that the binaural system detects a target best when having an accurate estimate of the “masker profile.” We add that this depends on the masker IPD statistics, i.e., on $\gamma_{M,lp}(t)$, but not on its power profile. Therefore, our model based on IPD statistics alone appears to account for both sluggish as well as fast binaural processing data.

Simulating the four different paradigms with the same model supports our hypothesis that binaural processing speed, similar to monaural processing speed, is only limited by peripheral processing. Apparent sluggishness results from higher-level analysis of masker IPD statistics. In perceptual terms, this means that sluggishness occurs whenever a task requires the listener to adapt to a change in perceived width in order to be receptive to the target. According to Singh and Bharadwaj (2021), this is no longer possible for modulations above about 10 Hz. They further pointed out that monaural and binaural modulation share the same transitions to a flutter for modulation frequencies above about 7 to 10 Hz. This corresponds to periods of 100 to 143 ms which matches well with the duration of threshold convergence observed by, e.g., Kollmeier and Gilkey (1990). As Ross *et al.* (2014) concluded from neuromagnetic responses to binaural beats that perception of moving sounds are limited by the cortical rate of object formation, and as modulations below about 7 Hz have been classified as crucial for object binding (Shinn-Cunningham *et al.*, 2017), we associate the origin of binaural sluggishness with object formation.

However, similar to the detection of Ocor or Phasewarp, the lateralization of a noise burst with an ITD alternating rapidly with diotic noise segments (Reed *et al.*, 2016) does not result in a sluggish integration of IPD, because the two interleaved streams form spatially distinct objects. Instead of, as previous models, slowly averaging instantaneous IPD on the sensory level, the proposed concept allows to collect binaural information on fast sensory data and puts any slow adaptation on the already separated objects, as suggested by Yabe *et al.* (2001). The concept is in line with typical duration dependence phenomena as characterized by Hafter *et al.* (1979), Hafter and Dye (1983), Houtgast and Plomp (1968), and Stecker (2014) including the knee point in N_0S_π thresholds as a function of signal duration at about 200 ms (Wilson and Fugleberg, 1987). It further agrees with the threshold decay measured by Kolarik and Culling (2009) for discriminating between two correlated or uncorrelated noise intervals, both containing a delayed noise of different length, differing only in the sign of the ITD. For short probe bursts, higher thresholds were observed compared to a condition where one interval contained only diotic noise and thus differed in coherence. The additional coherence cue is thought to cause the difference in thresholds. However, the similar time scales involved in object formation and integration suggest that both mechanisms contribute to the stable perception of an auditory object. In future works, the proposed model can be extended by subsequent temporal integration to account for saturating sensitivity at longer signals.

The proposed model captured the supposedly contradictory characteristics of the data, although different tasks that led to different conclusions on the binaural processing speed were simulated with the same model using the same temporal processing parameters. Only the internal-noise parameters σ_{bin} and σ_{mon} were changed between different tasks. The double-sided exponential window with its fixed ERD of

$2\tau = 60$ ms is similar to the ERDs obtained by Boehnke *et al.* (2002) for detecting dynamic changes in interaural correlation and those obtained by Kollmeier and Gilkey (1990), each by assuming temporal integration of interaural correlation. Although Grantham and Wightman (1979) fitted substantially larger ERDs than Kollmeier and Gilkey (1990), their data are also well explained by the present model and $2\tau = 60$ ms. Simulations include the relationship of conditions on binaural and monaural detection, which differ in the “sluggishness data” [Figs. 4(A) and 4(B)] but not in the “fast processing data” [Figs. 4(C) and 4(D)]. Although the model captures the key characteristics of the data, some details are not accurately reproduced, as addressed in Sec. II. These are mainly attributed to the fact that this model was designed as simple as possible to focus on simulating the hypothesized origin of binaural sluggishness.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

Psychoacoustic data sets that previously required very different binaural processing speeds can now be successfully simulated with the same model and without changing the temporal model parameters. Different effective processing speeds for the different tasks are facilitated by fast interaural cue encoding but a slow adaptation process to a change in the IPD statistics of the masker. Sluggishness kicks in when simulating detection in a masker with changing IPD statistics while for everything else the model is currently very fast. In our preceding study we demonstrated how a signal- and task-driven across-frequency interference of IPD statistics can resolve an apparent contradiction about the required filter bandwidth (Eurich *et al.*, 2022). The present study is an analogous strategy in the time domain to resolve an equally long-lasting apparent contradiction about the processing speed of the binaural system: It is very fast and very sluggish at the same time.

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¹For consistent processing in the two internal representations used in the model, the average over an ensemble of stimulus tokens was taken for numerator and denominator together instead of, as used in Encke and Dietz (2022), separately. This is irrelevant for the present simulations as it only negotiates differences between the left and right signals’ amplitudes.

Akeroyd, M. A., and Bernstein, L. R. (2001). “The variation across time of sensitivity to interaural disparities: Behavioral measurements and quantitative analyses,” *J. Acoust. Soc. Am.* **110**(5), 2516–2526.

- Bernstein, L. R., and Trahiotis, C. (2017). "Binaural detection-based estimates of precision of coding of interaural temporal disparities across center frequency," *J. Acoust. Soc. Am.* **141**(5), 3973.
- Bernstein, L. R., Trahiotis, C., Akeroyd, M. A., and Hartung, K. (2001). "Sensitivity to brief changes of interaural time and interaural intensity," *J. Acoust. Soc. Am.* **109**(4), 1604–1615.
- Bischof, N. F., Aublin, P. G., and Seeber, B. U. (2023). "Fast processing models effects of reflections on binaural unmasking," *Acta Acust.* **7**, 11.
- Boehnke, S. E., Hall, S. E., and Marquardt, T. (2002). "Detection of static and dynamic changes in interaural correlation," *J. Acoust. Soc. Am.* **112**(4), 1617–1626.
- Breebaart, J., van de Par, S., and Kohlrausch, A. (2001). "Binaural processing model based on contralateral inhibition. I. Model structure," *J. Acoust. Soc. Am.* **110**(2), 1074–1088.
- Buss, E., and Hall, J. W., III (2011). "Effects of non-simultaneous masking on the binaural masking level difference," *J. Acoust. Soc. Am.* **129**(2), 907–919.
- Culling, J. F., and Mansell, E. R. (2013). "Speech intelligibility among modulated and spatially distributed noise sources," *J. Acoust. Soc. Am.* **133**(4), 2254–2261.
- Culling, J. F., and Summerfield, Q. (1998). "Measurements of the binaural temporal window using a detection task," *J. Acoust. Soc. Am.* **103**(6), 3540–3553.
- Dietz, M., Ewert, S. D., Hohmann, V., and Kollmeier, B. (2008). "Coding of temporally fluctuating interaural timing disparities in a binaural processing model based on phase differences," *Brain Res.* **1220**, 234–245.
- Encke, J., and Dietz, M. (2022). "A hemispheric two-channel code accounts for binaural unmasking in humans," *Commun. Biol.* **5**(1), 1122.
- Eurich, B., Encke, J., Ewert, S. D., and Dietz, M. (2022). "Lower interaural coherence in off-signal bands impairs binaural detection," *J. Acoust. Soc. Am.* **151**(6), 3927–3936.
- Gatehouse, S., and Akeroyd, M. (2006). "Two-eared listening in dynamic situations," *Int. J. Audiol.* **45**, 120–124.
- Grantham, D. W. (1982). "Detectability of time-varying interaural correlation in narrow-band noise stimuli," *J. Acoust. Soc. Am.* **72**(4), 1178–1184.
- Grantham, D. W., and Wightman, F. L. (1979). "Detectability of a pulsed tone in the presence of a masker with time-varying interaural correlation," *J. Acoust. Soc. Am.* **65**, 1509–1517.
- Green, D. M., and Swets, J. A. (1966). *Signal Detection Theory and Psychophysics* (Peninsula, Los Altos Hills, CA).
- Hacker, M. J., and Ratcliff, R. (1979). "A revisited table of d' for M-alternative forced choice," *Percept. Psychophys.* **26**(2), 168–170.
- Haftner, E. R., and Dye, R. H. (1983). "Detection of interaural differences of time in trains of high-frequency clicks as a function of interclick interval and number," *J. Acoust. Soc. Am.* **73**(2), 644–651.
- Haftner, E. R., Dye, R. H., and Gilkey, R. H. (1979). "Lateralization of tonal signals which have neither onsets nor offsets," *J. Acoust. Soc. Am.* **65**(2), 471–477.
- Hauth, C. F., and Brand, T. (2018). "Modeling sluggishness in binaural unmasking of speech for maskers with time-varying interaural phase differences," *Trends Hear.* **22**, 233121651775354.
- Hohmann, V. (2002). "Frequency analysis and synthesis using a Gammatone filterbank," *Acta Acust. Acust.* **88**(3), 433–442, available at <https://www.ingentaconnect.com/content/dav/aaua/2002/00000088/00000003/art00015>.
- Holube, I., Kinkel, M., and Kollmeier, B. (1998). "Binaural and monaural auditory filter bandwidths and time constants in probe tone detection experiments," *J. Acoust. Soc. Am.* **104**(4), 2412–2425.
- Houtgast, T., and Plomp, R. (1968). "Lateralization threshold of a signal in noise," *J. Acoust. Soc. Am.* **44**(3), 807–812.
- Just, D., and Bamler, R. (1994). "Phase statistics of interferograms with applications to synthetic aperture radar," *Appl. Opt.* **33**(20), 4361–4368.
- Kolarik, A. J., and Culling, J. F. (2009). "Measurement of the binaural temporal window using a lateralisation task," *Hear. Res.* **248**(1-2), 60–68.
- Kollmeier, B., and Gilkey, R. H. (1990). "Binaural forward and backward masking: Evidence for sluggishness in binaural detection," *J. Acoust. Soc. Am.* **87**(4), 1709–1719.
- Lüddemann, H., Riedel, H., and Kollmeier, B. (2007). "Logarithmic scaling of interaural cross correlation: A model based on evidence from psychophysics and EEG," in *Hearing—From Sensory Processing to Perception*, edited by B. Kollmeier, G. Klump, V. Hohmann, U. Langemann, M. Mauermann, S. Uppenkamp, and J. Verhey (Springer, Berlin, Heidelberg), pp. 379–388.
- McFadden, D. (1966). "Masking-level differences with continuous and with burst masking noise," *J. Acoust. Soc. Am.* **40**(6), 1414–1419.
- McNemar, Q. (1969). *Psychological Statistics*, 4th ed. (Wiley, New York).
- Reed, D. K., Dietz, M., Josupeit, A., and van de Par, S. (2016). "Lateralization of stimuli with alternating interaural time differences: The role of monaural envelope cues," *J. Acoust. Soc. Am.* **139**(1), 30–40.
- Robinson, D. E., and Trahiotis, C. (1972). "Effects of signal duration and masker duration on detectability under diotic and dichotic listening conditions," *Percept. Psychophys.* **12**(4), 333–334.
- Ross, B., Miyazaki, T., Thompson, J., Jamali, S., and Fujioka, T. (2014). "Human cortical responses to slow and fast binaural beats reveal multiple mechanisms of binaural hearing," *J. Neurophysiol.* **112**(8), 1871–1884.
- Shinn-Cunningham, B., Best, V., and Lee, A. K. C. (2017). "Auditory object formation and selection," in *The Auditory System at the Cocktail Party*, Springer Handbook of Auditory Research Vol. 60 (Springer, Cham), pp. 7–40.
- Singh, R., and Bharadwaj, H. M. (2021). "Cortical temporal integration window for binaural cues accounts for sluggish auditory spatial perception," *bioRxiv*.
- Siveke, I., Ewert, S. D., Grothe, B., and Wiegrebe, L. (2008). "Psychophysical and physiological evidence for fast binaural processing," *J. Neurosci.* **28**(9), 2043–2052.
- Stecker, G. C. (2014). "Temporal weighting functions for interaural time and level differences. IV. Effects of carrier frequency," *J. Acoust. Soc. Am.* **136**(6), 3221–3232.
- Viemeister, N. F., and Wakefield, G. H. (1989). "Multiple looks and temporal integration," *J. Acoust. Soc. Am.* **86**(S1), S23.
- Wilson, R. H., and Fugleberg, R. A. (1987). "Influence of signal duration on the masking-level difference," *J. Speech. Lang. Hear. Res.* **30**(3), 330–334.
- Witton, C., Green, G. G. R., Rees, A., and Henning, G. B. (2000). "Monaural and binaural detection of sinusoidal phase modulation of a 500-Hz tone," *J. Acoust. Soc. Am.* **108**(4), 1826–1833.
- Yabe, H., Winkler, I., Czigler, I., Koyama, S., Kakigi, R., Sutoh, T., Hiruma, T., and Kaneko, S. (2001). "Organizing sound sequences in the human brain: The interplay of auditory streaming and temporal integration," *Brain Res.* **897**(1), 222–227.
- Yasin, I., and Henning, G. B. (2012). "The effects of noise-bandwidth, noise-fringe duration, and temporal signal location on the binaural masking-level difference," *J. Acoust. Soc. Am.* **132**(1), 327–338.
- Yost, W. A. (1985). "Prior stimulation and the masking-level difference," *J. Acoust. Soc. Am.* **78**(3), 901–907.
- Zwicker, E., and Fastl, H. (1999). *Masking* (Springer, Berlin), Vol. 22, pp. 61–110.